

E3.4 Final prototype of the inclusion of data lifecycle management for adaptive edge intelligence

v1.0

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**Programa de Universalización de
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I+D**

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1 Introduction

This document outlines the architecture and operational components for the final prototype for data management and adaptive learning in 6G. This prototype handles the data life cycle to achieve easy AI data interchange between nodes and allows the ML models to adapt to dynamic environmental changes. It includes all the distributed and handling mechanisms needed to achieve the project's aims.

2 Proposed Architecture for the final design

This section outlines the architecture designed to support adaptive edge intelligence through efficient data lifecycle management. The architecture consists of cloud and edge computing infrastructures that work in tandem to provide real-time data processing, storage, and analysis. It integrates key components like OpenTelemetry, InfluxDB, Prometheus, and Kubernetes to monitor, collect, and analyze system metrics. These components are essential for ensuring the scalability, flexibility, and responsiveness of machine learning models in dynamic environments. We will explore the cloud infrastructure, architectural layout, and specific roles of each service and component in detail.

2.1 Cloud infrastructure

Server	Configuration	Role	Kubernetes Cluster	Namespace Configuration	Functionality
Higher End Server (Cloud)	4 cores, 512 GB RAM, 2048 GB disk, GPU performance similar or superior to NVIDIA Tesla T4 or NVIDIA Tesla V100.	Represents the higher-end cloud infrastructure.	Hosts a Kubernetes cluster managed by OpenNebula.	-MLOps Namespace: Dedicated namespace for machine learning operations, including model training, inference, and resource allocation. - Telemetry Namespace: Namespace for OPTARE telemetry data aggregation and analysis.	-Aggregates telemetry data from the Edge server. -Hosts the MLOps pipeline for training and deploying machine learning models.
Edge Server	48 cores, 128 GB RAM, 2048 GB dis	Represents the edge computing infrastructure	Hosts a Kubernetes cluster managed by OpenNebula.	Default namespace	-Executes the holoportation application stack and core network functionalities. -Request the resource allocation model re-training from the MLOps pipeline hosted on the Higher End server. - Dynamically scales the holoportation application stack based on recommendations from the resource allocation model. -Sends telemetry data to the Higher End server for aggregation and analysis.

Table 1 - Testbench components

2.2 Architecture

Figure 1 - Final Design architecture

Component	Purpose	Justification
OTel Prometheus Client	To collect, process, and export metrics from Prometheus service.	Supports receiving metrics from the Prometheus service.
OTel k8s cloud Server	To collect, process, and export Kubernetes resources metrics.	Crucial for gaining real-time insights into system performance, enhances the ability to detect and resolve issues.
Prometheus (Observability Backend)	To collect and store metrics from services, offering a platform for real-time monitoring and alerts.	Supports data visibility and metric management, crucial for monitoring system performance and health, enabling proactive and reactive adjustments in the infrastructure.
InfluxDB (Observability Backend)	To serve as a time-series database for storing metrics and events collected by OTel.	Optimized for the storage and querying of time-series data, facilitates the analysis of trends and patterns in data, essential for data-driven decision-making and data lifecycle management.
Feast (Feature Store)	To manage the storage, access, and serving of data features for ML model training and inference.	Key for the reuse of data features and ensuring consistency and quality in model training, supporting transfer learning and efficiency in data lifecycle management.
Apache Airflow	To orchestrate and automate complex workflows and scheduled tasks in data processing and ML operations.	Facilitates the coordination of task dependencies and the automation of ETL and ML workflows, improving reproducibility, efficiency, and scalability in data lifecycle management and ML operations.

Component	Purpose	Justification
Grafana	To visualize metrics, logs, and other data collected from various sources in real-time.	Essential for creating interactive and insightful dashboards, aiding in the monitoring and analysis of system health and performance. Enhances data visibility and helps in quickly identifying and diagnosing issues in a user-friendly manner.
Dummy App	Create metrics	Creates metrics to check if these are visible in other apps.

Table 2 - Components

2.3 Components and Services description

This section provides a detailed overview of the key components and services that form the foundation of the system architecture. Each component plays a critical role in ensuring the efficient collection, processing, and management of data, while the services enable seamless communication, resource orchestration, and operational functionality.

2.3.1 Feature Store service

Feast (Feature Store) is a customizable operational data system that re-uses existing infrastructure to manage and serve machine learning features to real time models.

Feast allows ML platform teams to:

Make features consistently available for training and serving by managing an *offline store* (to process historical data for scale-out batch scoring or model training), a low-latency *online store* (to power real-time prediction), and a battle-tested *feature server* (to serve pre-computed features online).

Avoid data leakage by generating point-in-time correct feature sets so data scientists can focus on feature engineering rather than debugging error-prone dataset joining logic. This ensure that future feature values do not leak to models during training.

Decouple ML from data infrastructure by providing a single data access layer that abstracts feature storage from feature retrieval, ensuring models remain portable as you move from training models to serving models, from batch models to real time models, and from one data infra system to another.

Figure 2 - Feast

2.3.2 OTEL collector

The OpenTelemetry Collector offers a vendor-agnostic implementation of how to receive, process and export telemetry data. It removes the need to run, operate, and maintain multiple agents/collectors. This works with improved scalability and supports open-source observability data formats (e.g. Jaeger, Prometheus, Fluent Bit, etc.) sending to one or more open source or commercial backends. The local Collector agent is the default location to which instrumentation libraries export their telemetry data.

Figure 3 - Otel Collector

2.3.2.1 OTEL Prometheus collector

The OTEL Prometheus collector is responsible for collecting metrics from the Prometheus service and send them to influxDB.

2.3.2.2 OTEL K8s collector

The OTEL K8s collector is responsible for collecting Kubernetes resources metrics and send them to influxDB.

2.3.3 Prometheus

Prometheus is an open-source systems monitoring and alerting toolkit, it collects and stores its metrics as time series data, i.e. metrics information is stored with the timestamp at which it was recorded, alongside optional key-value pairs called labels.

2.3.4 InfluxDB

InfluxDB is an open-source time series database. It is used for storage and retrieval of time series data in fields such as operations monitoring, application metrics, Internet of Things sensor data, and real-time analytics.

2.3.5 Grafana

Grafana is a multi-platform open-source analytics and interactive visualization web application. It can produce charts, graphs, and alerts for the web when connected to supported data sources.

2.3.6 Dummy App

The dummy app creates a metric, that can be visualized in influxdb to ensure that everything is working correctly.

2.3.7 ETL

ETL is the mechanism encharge of synchronize the observability backend (time-series data base) with the offline databa (warehouse), which serves as the data source for our feature store platform. This process will be executed through the Apache Airflow workflow orchestration, establishing connections to the time-series and PostgreSQL databases.

3 Installation of final design

This section provides comprehensive installation instructions for deploying the final design of the data lifecycle management system. It covers the deployment of critical services like PostgreSQL, Grafana, InfluxDB, and the OTel Collector, along with configuration details for Apache Airflow and the Feature Store. Each service plays a crucial role in data collection, processing, and visualization, ensuring that users have the tools needed to manage and monitor system performance. The installation steps are presented with explanations of key configurations to ensure seamless setup and operation.

IMPORTANT

Passwords and tokens are omitted in this document for security reasons.

3.1 Postgres

To deploy postgres run the following commands:

```
kubectl apply -f postgres-pv.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: postgres-pv
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  persistentVolumeReclaimPolicy: Retain
  hostPath:
    path: "/mnt/data/postgres"
```

```
kubectl apply -f postgres.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: postgres-pvc
spec:
  accessModes:
```

```
- ReadWriteOnce
resources:
  requests:
    storage: 10Gi
  volumeName: postgres-pv
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: postgres
  namespace: observability
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: postgres
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: postgres
    spec:
      securityContext:
        fsGroup: 999
      containers:
        - name: postgres
          image: postgres:16
          args: ["-c", "max_connections=500"]
          ports:
            - containerPort: 5432
          env:
            - name: POSTGRES_DB
              value: "*****"
            - name: POSTGRES_USER
              value: "*****"
            - name: POSTGRES_PASSWORD
              value: "*****"
            - name: PGDATA
              value: /var/lib/postgresql/data/pgdata
          volumeMounts:
            - mountPath: /var/lib/postgresql/data
              name: postgres-storage
      securityContext:
```

```
    runAsUser: 999
    runAsGroup: 999
  volumes:
  - name: postgres-storage
    persistentVolumeClaim:
      claimName: postgres-pvc
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: postgres
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: postgres
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 5432
    targetPort: 5432
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: postgres-nodeport
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: postgres
  type: NodePort
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 5432
    targetPort: 5432
    nodePort: 30104
```

3.2 Grafana

To deploy grafana run the following command:

```
kubectl apply -f grafana.yaml
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: grafana
  namespace: observability
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: grafana
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: grafana
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: grafana
        image: grafana/grafana:latest
        ports:
        - containerPort: 3000
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: grafana
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: grafana
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 3000
    targetPort: 3000
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
```

```
metadata:
  name: grafana-nodeport
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: grafana
  type: NodePort
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 3000
    targetPort: 3000
    nodePort: 30103
```

Service is exposed in port 30103. First time accessing Grafana it will ask to set a password.

3.3 InfluxDb

To deploy influxdb run the following commands:

```
kubectl apply -f influx-db-pv.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: influxdb-pv
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
  - ReadWriteOnce
  persistentVolumeReclaimPolicy: Retain
  hostPath:
    path: "/mnt/data/influxdb"
```

```
kubectl apply -f influxdb.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: influxdb-pvc
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: influxdb
  namespace: observability
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: influxdb
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: influxdb
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: influxdb
          image: influxdb:latest
          ports:
            - containerPort: 8086
          env:
            - name: DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_MODE
              value: "setup"
            - name: DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_USERNAME
              value: "*****"
            - name: DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_PASSWORD
              value: "*****"
            - name: DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_ORG
              value: "*****"
```

```
- name: DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_BUCKET
  value: "*****"
- name: DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_ADMIN_TOKEN
  value: "*****"
volumeMounts:
- mountPath: /var/lib/influxdb
  name: influxdb-storage
volumes:
- name: influxdb-storage
  persistentVolumeClaim:
    claimName: influxdb-pvc
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: influxdb
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: influxdb
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 8086
    targetPort: 8086
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: influxdb-nodeport
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: influxdb
  type: NodePort
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 8086
    targetPort: 8086
    nodePort: 30102
```

3.4 OTEL Collector

To deploy OTEL-prometheus and OTEL-k8s-metrics run the following commands:

```
kubectl apply -f otel-prometheus.yaml
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: otel-prometheus
  namespace: observability
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: otel-prometheus
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: otel-prometheus
    spec:
      serviceAccountName: otel-prometheus-sa
      containers:
        - name: otel-collector
          image: ghcr.io/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-collector-
releases/opentelemetry-collector-contrib:0.88.0
          ports:
            - containerPort: 9090
            - containerPort: 4317
            - containerPort: 55681
            - containerPort: 8086
          volumeMounts:
            - name: config-volume
              mountPath: /etc/otel
            - name: host-fs
              mountPath: /hostfs
          env:
            - name: K8S_NODE_NAME
              valueFrom:
                fieldRef:
                  fieldPath: spec.nodeName
            - name: OTEL_RESOURCE_ATTRIBUTES
```

```
        value: k8s.node.name=$(K8S_NODE_NAME)
    command:
      - "/otelcol-contrib"
      - "--config=/etc/otel/config.yaml"
    volumes:
      - name: config-volume
        configMap:
          name: otel-prometheus-config
      - name: host-fs
        hostPath:
          path: /
          type: Directory
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: ConfigMap
metadata:
  name: otel-prometheus-config
  namespace: observability
data:
  config.yaml: |
    receivers:
      otlp:
        protocols:
          http:
          grpc:
      prometheus:
        config:
          scrape_configs:
            - job_name: 'otel-prometheus'
              scrape_interval: 10s
              static_configs:
                - targets: ['172.27.13.242:9090']
    processors:
      batch:
      memory_limiter:
        check_interval: 1s
        limit_percentage: 50
        spike_limit_percentage: 10
      resourcedetection/env:
        detectors:
          - env
    exporters:
```

```
logging: {}
influxdb:
  endpoint: "http://influxdb.observability.svc.cluster.local:8086"
  timeout: 500ms
  org: "*****"
  bucket: "*****"
  token: "*****"
  span_dimensions:
    - service.name
    - span.name
  log_record_dimensions:
    - service.name
  metrics_schema: telegraf-prometheus-v1
  sending_queue:
    enabled: true
    num_consumers: 3
    queue_size: 10
  retry_on_failure:
    enabled: true
    initial_interval: 1s
    max_interval: 3s
    max_elapsed_time: 10s
service:
  pipelines:
    metrics:
      receivers: [otlp, prometheus]
      processors: [resourcedetection/env, memory_limiter, batch]
      exporters: [logging, influxdb]
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: otel-prometheus
  namespace: observability
spec:
  ports:
    - port: 4317
      targetPort: 4317
      name: otlp-grpc
    - port: 55681
      targetPort: 55681
      name: otlp-http
```

```
- port: 9090
  targetPort: 9090
  name: prometheus
selector:
  app: otel-prometheus
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: ServiceAccount
metadata:
  name: otel-prometheus-sa
  namespace: observability
---
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: ClusterRole
metadata:
  name: otel-prometheus-role
rules:
  - apiGroups: [""]
    resources: ["nodes", "pods", "services", "namespaces",
"resourcequotas","replicationcontrollers"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
  - apiGroups: [""]
    resources: ["nodes/stats", "configmaps", "events", "nodes/proxy"]
    verbs: ["get"]
  - apiGroups: ["apps"]
    resources: ["replicasets","daemonsets", "deployments", "statefulsets"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
  - apiGroups: ["batch"]
    resources: ["jobs", "cronjobs"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
  - apiGroups: ["autoscaling"]
    resources: ["horizontalpodautoscalers"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
---
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: ClusterRoleBinding
metadata:
  name: otel-prometheus-binding
roleRef:
  apiGroup: rbac.authorization.k8s.io
  kind: ClusterRole
  name: otel-prometheus-role
```

```
subjects:
  - kind: ServiceAccount
    name: otel-prometheus-sa
    namespace: observability

kubectl apply -f otel-k8s-metrics.yaml

apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics
  namespace: observability
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: otel-collector-k8s-metrics
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: otel-collector-k8s-metrics
    spec:
      serviceAccountName: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-sa
      containers:
        - name: otel-collector
          image: ghcr.io/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-collector-
releases/opentelemetry-collector-contrib:0.88.0
          ports:
            - containerPort: 8888
            - containerPort: 4317
            - containerPort: 55681
            - containerPort: 8086
          volumeMounts:
            - name: config-volume
              mountPath: /etc/otel
            - name: host-fs
              mountPath: /hostfs
      env:
        - name: K8S_NODE_NAME
          valueFrom:
            fieldRef:
              fieldPath: spec.nodeName
        - name: OTEL_RESOURCE_ATTRIBUTES
```

```
        value: k8s.node.name=$(K8S_NODE_NAME)
    command:
      - "/otelcol-contrib"
      - "--config=/etc/otel/config.yaml"
  volumes:
    - name: config-volume
      configMap:
        name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-config
    - name: host-fs
      hostPath:
        path: /
        type: Directory
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: ConfigMap
metadata:
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-config
  namespace: observability
data:
  config.yaml: |
    receivers:
      otlp:
        protocols:
          http:
          grpc:
    k8s_cluster:
      auth_type: serviceAccount
      node_conditions_to_report:
        - Ready
        - MemoryPressure
      allocatable_types_to_report:
        - cpu
        - memory
    kubeletstats:
      collection_interval: 20s
      auth_type: "serviceAccount"
      endpoint: "https://172.27.13.237:10250"
      extra_metadata_labels:
        - k8s.volume.type
      insecure_skip_verify: true
      metric_groups:
        - container
```

```
- pod
- volume
- node
hostmetrics:
  collection_interval: 10s
  root_path: /hostfs
  scrapers:
    cpu:
      metrics:
        system.cpu.utilization:
          enabled: true
    disk: null
    filesystem:
      exclude_fs_types:
        fs_types:
          - autofs
          - binfmt_misc
          - bpf
          - cgroup2
          - configfs
          - debugfs
          - devpts
          - devtmpfs
          - fusectl
          - hugetlbfs
          - iso9660
          - mqueue
          - nsfs
          - overlay
          - proc
          - procfs
          - pstore
          - rpc_pipefs
          - securityfs
          - selinuxfs
          - squashfs
          - sysfs
          - tracefs
        match_type: strict
      exclude_mount_points:
        match_type: regexp
      mount_points:
```

```
    - /dev/*
    - /proc/*
    - /sys/*
    - /run/k3s/containerd/*
    - /run/containerd/runc/*
    - /var/lib/docker/*
    - /var/lib/kubelet/*
    - /snap/*
  load: null
  memory:
    metrics:
      system.memory.utilization:
        enabled: true
    network: null

processors:
  batch:
  memory_limiter:
    check_interval: 1s
    limit_percentage: 50
    spike_limit_percentage: 10
  k8sattributes:
    auth_type: 'serviceAccount'
    extract:
      metadata:
        - k8s.namespace.name
        - k8s.pod.name
        - k8s.pod.start_time
        - k8s.pod.uid
        - k8s.deployment.name
        - k8s.node.name
  resourcedetection/env:
    detectors:
      - env

exporters:
  logging: {}
  influxdb:
    endpoint: "http://influxdb.observability.svc.cluster.local:8086"
    timeout: 500ms
    org: "*****"
    bucket: "*****"
    token: "*****"
```

```
span_dimensions:
- service.name
- span.name
log_record_dimensions:
- service.name
metrics_schema: telegraf-prometheus-v1
sending_queue:
  enabled: true
  num_consumers: 3
  queue_size: 10
retry_on_failure:
  enabled: true
  initial_interval: 1s
  max_interval: 3s
  max_elapsed_time: 10s
service:
  pipelines:
    metrics:
      receivers: [otlp, k8s_cluster, hostmetrics, kubeletstats]
      processors: [k8sattributes, resourcedetection/env, memory_limiter,
batch]
      exporters: [logging, influxdb]
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics
  namespace: observability
spec:
  ports:
    - port: 4317
      targetPort: 4317
      name: otlp-grpc
    - port : 55681
      targetPort: 55681
      name: otlp-http
    - port: 8888
      targetPort: 8888
      name: k8s-metrics
  selector:
    app: otel-collector-k8s-metrics
---
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: ServiceAccount
metadata:
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-sa
  namespace: observability
---
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: ClusterRole
metadata:
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-role
rules:
  - apiGroups: [""]
    resources: ["nodes", "pods", "services", "namespaces",
"resourcequotas","replicationcontrollers"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
  - apiGroups: [""]
    resources: ["nodes/stats", "configmaps", "events", "nodes/proxy"]
    verbs: ["get"]
  - apiGroups: ["apps"]
    resources: ["replicasets","daemonsets", "deployments", "statefulsets"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
  - apiGroups: ["batch"]
    resources: ["jobs", "cronjobs"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
  - apiGroups: ["autoscaling"]
    resources: ["horizontalpodautoscalers"]
    verbs: ["get", "list", "watch"]
---
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: ClusterRoleBinding
metadata:
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-binding
roleRef:
  apiGroup: rbac.authorization.k8s.io
  kind: ClusterRole
  name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-role
subjects:
  - kind: ServiceAccount
    name: otel-collector-k8s-metrics-sa
    namespace: observability
```

3.5 ETL

Customized Airflow Image

We need to create an Apache Airflow image that includes the dependencies we will need to run our DAGs. Below is the customized image with the dependencies influxdb-client and psycopg2-binary:

```
# Extend from the official Airflow image
FROM apache/airflow:2.8.4
# Switch to root user to install dependencies
USER root
# Install the necessary dependencies
RUN pip install --no-cache-dir influxdb-client psycopg2-binary
# Switch back to the airflow user
USER airflow
```

To deploy ETL run the following commands:

```
kubectl apply -f pv.yaml
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-airflow-dags
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 1Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  hostPath:
    path: /mnt/data/airflow/dags
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-airflow-logs
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  hostPath:
    path: /mnt/data/airflow/logs
---
apiVersion: v1
```

```
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-airflow-workers
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  hostPath:
    path: /mnt/data/airflow/workers
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-airflow-triggerer
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  hostPath:
    path: /mnt/data/airflow/triggerer
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-airflow-redis
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 1Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  hostPath:
    path: /mnt/data/airflow/redis
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-airflow-postgresql
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
```

```
accessModes:
  - ReadWriteOnce
hostPath:
  path: /mnt/data/airflow/postgresql
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-logs-airflow-triggerer-0
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  persistentVolumeReclaimPolicy: Retain
  storageClassName: ""
  hostPath:
    path: /mnt/data/airflow/logs/triggerer
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-logs-airflow-worker
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 10Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  persistentVolumeReclaimPolicy: Retain
  hostPath:
    path: "/mnt/data/airflow/logs-worker"
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolume
metadata:
  name: pv-redis-db-airflow-redis
spec:
  capacity:
    storage: 1Gi
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  persistentVolumeReclaimPolicy: Retain
```

```
hostPath:
  path: "/mnt/data/airflow/redis-db"
```

kubectl apply -f pvc.yaml

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: airflow-dags
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 1Gi
  volumeName: pv-airflow-dags
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: airflow-logs
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
  volumeName: pv-airflow-logs
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: data-airflow-postgresql-0
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
```

```
    volumeName: pv-airflow-postgresql
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: airflow-redis
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 1Gi
    volumeName: pv-airflow-redis
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: airflow-triggerer
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
    volumeName: pv-airflow-triggerer
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: airflow-workers
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
    volumeName: pv-airflow-workers
---
apiVersion: v1
```

```
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: logs-airflow-triggerer-0
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
  volumeName: pv-logs-airflow-triggerer-0
  storageClassName: ""
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: logs-airflow-worker-0
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 10Gi
  storageClassName: ""
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: redis-db-airflow-redis-0
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 1Gi
  storageClassName: ""
```

```
kubectl apply -f sc.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: storage.k8s.io/v1
kind: StorageClass
metadata:
  name: standard
provisioner: kubernetes.io/no-provisioner
volumeBindingMode: WaitForFirstConsumer
```

Create airflow directories and apply following settings:

```
sudo mkdir -p /mnt/data/airflow/dags
sudo mkdir -p /mnt/data/airflow/logs
sudo mkdir -p /mnt/data/airflow/logs-worker
sudo mkdir -p /mnt/data/airflow/postgresql
sudo mkdir -p /mnt/data/airflow/redis-db
sudo mkdir -p /mnt/data/airflow/triggerer

sudo chown -R root:root /mnt/data/airflow/dags
sudo chmod -R 777 /mnt/data/airflow/dags

sudo chown -R root:root /mnt/data/airflow/logs
sudo chmod -R 777 /mnt/data/airflow/logs

sudo chown -R root:root /mnt/data/airflow/logs-worker
sudo chmod -R 777 /mnt/data/airflow/logs-worker

sudo chown -R root:root /mnt/data/airflow/postgresql
sudo chmod -R 777 /mnt/data/airflow/postgresql

sudo chown -R root:root /mnt/data/airflow/redis-db
sudo chmod -R 777 /mnt/data/airflow/redis-db

sudo chown -R root:root /mnt/data/airflow/triggerer
sudo chmod -R 777 /mnt/data/airflow/triggerer
```

Install Airflow

```
helm install airflow apache-airflow/airflow --namespace airflow --
create-namespace --debug
helm show values apache-airflow/airflow > values.yaml
```

Modify values.yaml

Line 267: executor: "KubernetesExecutor"

```
helm upgrade --install airflow apache-airflow/airflow --namespace
airflow --debug --values values.yaml
```

Finally, it is provided a nodePort service to access UI.

```
kubectl apply -f svc-airflow-webserver.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: airflow-webserver-nodeport
  namespace: airflow
spec:
  type: NodePort
  ports:
    - name: airflow-ui
      port: 8080
      protocol: TCP
      targetPort: 8080
      nodePort: 30106
  selector:
    component: webserver
    release: airflow
status:
  loadBalancer: {}
```

3.6 Dummy App

Dummy app was set to create some metrics to send to Otel Collector.

To deploy this app run the following command:

```
kubectl apply -f dummy-python-deployment.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: dummy-python-deployment
  namespace: observability-backend
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
```

```
    app: dummy-python
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: dummy-python
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: dummy-python
          image: jsantosoptare/dummy:latest
          ports:
            - containerPort: 8080
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: dummy-python-service
  namespace: observability-backend
spec:
  type: NodePort
  selector:
    app: dummy-python
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8080
      targetPort: 8080
      nodePort: 30107
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: dummy-python-clusterip-service
  namespace: observability-backend
spec:
  type: ClusterIP
  selector:
    app: dummy-python
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8080
      targetPort: 8080
```

3.7 Feature Store

Feast is an open-source framework for storing and serving features to machine learning models. It aims to facilitate the retrieval of feature data from different sources and to this end provides a unified environment for feature management.

To deploy the FeatureStore run the following commands:

```
kubectl apply -f feature-store-deployment.yaml
```

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: feature-store-deployment
  namespace: observability
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: feature-store-deployment
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: feature-store-deployment
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: feature-store
          image: jsantosoptare/feast:latest
          ports:
            - containerPort: 8080
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: feature-store-service
  namespace: observability
spec:
  type: NodePort
  selector:
    app: feature-store-deployment
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8080
```

```

    targetPort: 8080
    nodePort: 30108
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: feature-store-service-internal
  namespace: observability
spec:
  selector:
    app: feature-store-deployment
  ports:
    - name: feature-store-internal
      port: 8080

```

To check if the installation was correctly, access this url: <http://url:30108/v2/ui/>

After the deployment is still needed to configure the feature store.

A feature.py file like this one is needed, where the features and offline data table is configured.

feature.py

```

# This is an example feature definition file
from datetime import timedelta
import pandas as pd
from feast import Entity, FeatureService, FeatureView, Field, PushSource,
RequestSource
from feast.infra.offline_stores.contrib.postgres_offline_store.postgres_source
import (
    PostgreSQLSource,
)
from feast.on_demand_feature_view import on_demand_feature_view
from feast.types import Float32, Float64, Int64, String
# Define an entity for the driver. You can think of an entity as a primary key
used to
# fetch features.
driver = Entity(name="metrics_test", join_keys=["deployment"])
driver_stats_source = PostgreSQLSource(
    name="metrics_service",
    query="SELECT * FROM metrics_test",
    timestamp_field="_time",
    #created_timestamp_column="created",
)
# Our parquet files contain sample data that includes a driver_id column,
timestamps and
# three feature column. Here we define a Feature View that will allow us to
serve this
# data to our model online.
metrics_features_view = FeatureView(
    # The unique name of this feature view. Two feature views in a single
    # project cannot have the same name

```

```

    name="metrics_feature",
    entities=[driver],
    ttl=timedelta(days=1),
    # The list of features defined below act as a schema to both define
features
    # for both materialization of features into a store, and are used as
references
    # during retrieval for building a training dataset or serving features
    schema=[
        Field(name="k8s_pod_cpu_time", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="k8s_pod_cpu_utilization", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="k8s_pod_network_io", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="container_cpu_time", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="container_cpu_utilization", dtype=Float32)
    ],
    online=True,
    source=driver_stats_source,
    # Tags are user defined key/value pairs that are attached to each
    # feature view
    #tags={"team": "ramp"},
)
metrics_features_service = FeatureService(
    name="metrics_feature",
    features=[metrics_features_view]
)

```

And a `feature_store.yaml` where the database info is present.

```

feature_store.yaml

project: feast client
# By default, the registry is a file (but can be turned into a more
scalable SQL-backed registry)
registry: data/registry.db
# The provider primarily specifies default offline / online stores &
storing the registry in a given cloud
provider: local
online_store:
    type: sqlite
    path: data/online_store.db
entity_key_serialization_version: 2
offline_store:
    type: postgres
    host: postgres.observability.svc.cluster.local
    port: 5432
    database: *****
    db_schema: *****
    user: *****
    password: *****

```

4 Integration

In this section, we explain the integration process for setting up the complete system architecture. We provide a step-by-step guide on how to configure the necessary components, including the feature store, telemetry collectors, and observability services. This integration ensures that data flows seamlessly from collection to storage, allowing for effective monitoring and decision-making. Each integration step is accompanied by detailed instructions and relevant code snippets to help users implement the system without issues.

<http://172.27.13.237:30108/v2/ui/#/>

Figure 4 - Different requests available

Step 1: Clone Repo

```
curl -X POST "http://feature-store-service-internal.observability.svc.cluster.local:8080/v2/clone_repo" \
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \
-d '{"feature.py": "https://gitlab.com/jsantos24/repo_clone/-/raw/main/feature.py",
"feature_store.yaml": "https://gitlab.com/jsantos24/repo_clone/-/raw/main/feature_store.yaml"}'
```

Step 2: Get Store

```
curl -L http://feature-store-service-internal.observability.svc.cluster.local:8080/v2/get\_store
```

Step 3: Get Offline Feature

```
curl -X POST "http://feature-store-service-internal.observability.svc.cluster.local:8080/v2/get_offline_features?startDate=2024-08-01T12:00:00&endDate=2024-08-02T14:00:00" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d '{"serviceName": ["dummy-python-deployment"]}'
```

Result :

200 OK

```
[
  {
    "container_cpu_time": 0.4078509091,
    "container_cpu_utilization": 0.0023405235,
    "deployment": "dummy-python-deployment",
    "event_date": "2024-08-02",
    "event_time": "14:00:00",
    "event_timestamp": 1722607200000,
    "k8s_pod_cpu_time": 0.394327,
    "k8s_pod_cpu_utilization": 0.0007106301,
    "k8s_pod_network_io": 10485.5454545455
  },

```

..... more data

```
]
```

Step 4: Get Online Feature

```
curl -X POST "http://feature-store-service-internal.observability.svc.cluster.local:8080/v2/get_online_features" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d '{"serviceName": ["dummy-python-deployment"]}'
```

Response:

200 OK

```
{
  "container_cpu_time": [1058.906982421875],
  "container_cpu_utilization": [0.0003983160713687539],
  "deployment": ["dummy-python-deployment"],
  "k8s_pod_cpu_time": [1058.9246826171875],
  "k8s_pod_cpu_utilization": [0.00040529746911488473],
  "k8s_pod_network_io": [89678048.0]
}
```